

WELLNESS TOURISM: A perspective article

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Abstract

Purpose

This paper examines the development and significant contributions in a growing array of relevant publications spanning from 1946 to date and discusses future developments of the wellness tourism topic until the year 2095.

Design/methodology/approach

This perspective study traces down the wellness tourism evolution research by reviewing and analysing an extant body of the relevant literature over the last 75 years. This paper builds a rigorous perspective review by examination of publications derived from several scientific domains, including tourism, medicine, economics, and social sciences.

Findings

As a result of this study, wellness tourism can be attributed as a profuse and proliferating research stream in the recent 75 years. Its relevance to significant aspects of life, such as health and also due to effects on human, social, and economic wellbeing, drives its proliferation. The paper anticipates the relevance and topicality of wellness tourism studies for academic research in the next 75 years.

Originality/value

This paper contributes to the theory by addressing the ambiguous nature of wellness tourism, recapping the debate on the most debated research questions, and revealing the perspectives for future research in this area.

Keywords: Health resorts, Health tourism, Wellness, Wellness Tourism, Wellbeing, Research perspectives.

Introduction

Wellness tourism is noted as one of the essential research themes in tourism studies as it pertains to a healthy lifestyle adoption (Nefiodow, 2006; Cassens et al., 2010) and because of the effects on economy and globalisation (Evans, 2008; Hall, 2013). It implies an expanding tourism niche encompassing individual or group travel to specialised resorts and destinations with the purpose of physical and mental health maintenance. Extant literature divides wellness tourism into two distinct research arrays, namely medical and wellbeing. The first involves illnesses surgical or therapeutic treatment in the domain of biological research while the second is more relevant to the more complex wellness research paradigm balancing of human mind, spirit, body, environment, and quality of life (Voigt and Pforr, 2013; Hartwell et al., 2018).

Wellness tourism is a steadily growing global market with a reported size of around \$639 billion in 2017 and is expected to reach the sales of around \$919 billion by 2022 (GWI, 2018). In this paper, we address the ambiguity implicit to wellness tourism by reviewing the recent trends and future progress of academic research in wellness tourism.

Past perspective 75 years of developments 1946-2020

People have been using spas for their wellbeing from ancient times as archaeological evidence for bathing in Egypt and Babylon points to nearly 3000 BCE. This era could mark the onset of wellness tourism, which proliferated further with an idolisation of antique Greek steam baths Laconia and, later, Roman baths of Tepidarium (Jackson, 1990). Humankind inherited a remarkable Hippocrates' quote from that era that best depicts the roots of healthcare and wellness: «the way to health is to have an aromatic bath and a scented massage every day.»

In the middle of the nineteenth century, the first wellness destinations were established near the springs of mineral waters (Hall, 2013). This era signified the birth of a nexus between health, wellness, and travel and led to the establishment of the new research perspective. Tourism researchers focused on the examination of spa resorts development in Europe (Gilbert, 1954; Haug, 1982; Goodrich and Goodrich, 1987) while the medical community broadly examined the development of resort therapy (Haggard, 1943). In the 1960s, medical researchers began to focus actively on therapeutical facets of tourism including patient rehabilitation (Grimm, 1960; Jordan, 1965; Snycheva and Iakovleva, 1965) and climatic treatments of several illnesses in various sanatoria locations (Ramakrishnan et al., 1961; Dawson et al., 1966).

To conceptualise the medical and wellness nexus, Antonovsky (1979) suggested a theoretical approach of Salutogenesis. This framework implies a healthcare provision, augmented by the incorporation of auxiliary factors into the treatment referred to as salutogenics that help to cope with the patient's stress to facilitate a positive outcome of the medical procedure. Several studies have further contributed to the Salutogenesis concept. Dilani (2008; 2009) built a contemporary ground for a Salutogenic approach by introducing a physical environment ecosystem that creates a positive ambience in healthcare institutions. Chrysikou (2014, 2017) blended salutogenics with a broader framework of ecopsychosociology (Engel, 1977) and adopted them for ageing and mental health context. Furthermore, the blending of the physical environment and patient therapy was determined to be an appropriate health provision strategy in medical and wellness tourism settings (Chrysikou et al., 2018). Niche clinical researchers suggest that classic patient care strategies would benefit if complemented with wellness approaches 'including ... acupuncture, yoga, tai chi, and meditation' (Prabhakar et al., 2019:14).

Simultaneously, tourism literature unveils three notable relevant research streams. They comprise health, wellness, and wellbeing conceptualisation and operationalisation (Ryff, 1989; Ryan and Deci, 2001; Filep, 2014); sustainability and impact on destinations, local communities, businesses and tourists (Waterman, 1993; Moscardo et al., 2013; Romão, 2018); tourist behavior in wellness tourism context (Diener and Suh, 1997, Kahneman and Krueger; 2006; Kim et al., 2015). Fig.1 depicts the conceptual framework of the wellness tourism research timeline.

In 2020, wellness tourism is gaining momentum as a lifestyle in developed countries has become more hedonistic (Smith and Puczkó, 2014). Thereby, we anticipate that this research stream will proliferate in the future.

Future perspective 75 years 2020-2095

Wellness tourism is a mega-market in the twenty-first century (Nefiodov, 2006). Human stress, demand for personalised services, ageing society, predispose its development (Voigt and Pforr, 2013). The holistic wellness tourism concept will

1
2 amalgamate health, wellbeing, hospitality, and transportation into an industry capable of
3 delivering numerous tourist service solutions (GWI, 2018). Salutogenics is likely to be a
4 core philosophy that will propel wellness tourism development in the next 75 years
5 (Chrysikou et al., 2018). Industry consolidation may foster a research stream aiming to
6 tackle the inconsistency of wellness tourism conceptualisation (Smith and Puczkó, 2014)
7 to help businesses and destinations to improve their positioning (Summit, 2011).
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10 Future research may examine the growth drivers of wellness tourism. They may
11 impact customers; therefore, consumer behavior studies would become essential. Future
12 researchers may also be prone to scrutinise the best practices of ESG strategies (Hood,
13 2018). The holistic wellness model will gear a change in the destination management
14 approach because customers will look for blended and coherent wellness tourist
15 destinations that offer an integrated health-wellness tourism concept (Hartwell et al.,
16 2018). In this line, the role of active holiday paradigms will increase with the proliferating
17 public interest in hiking, sports, and adventure spas, subsequently generating the attention
18 from academia (Summit, 2011).
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21 Sustainable wellness tourism concept is another research theme to receive an uplift in
22 future studies (Wolf et al., 2017). Future researchers may be enticed by the opportunities to
23 explain its effects on a destination's natural resources, local cultures, and if wellness
24 tourism is capable of delivering a unique customer experience (Romão, 2018). Future
25 studies may encompass advancements in territory branding, similar to Alpine Wellness and
26 Nordic Wellbeing regional initiatives (Summit, 2011). Prospective research will be driven
27 by technological advancements, mainly in ICTs that are influential for tourism (Buhalis
28 and Leung, 2018). Breakthroughs in medical treatments and technologies, such as 3D
29 printing, recreational cyborgs, real-time diagnostics, holographic data input, will feed up
30 the research in the literature (Meskó, 2018; Tarkkala et al., 2019). These studies will
31 examine positive technology effects on wellbeing, possibly, in the realm of wellness
32 tourism.
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35 Theses delineated research trends assume holistic wellness tourism development
36 optimistically, but, indeed, it cannot proceed without a hitch. Anticipated expansion may
37 be simultaneously accompanied by the 'growth illness' unveiling itself in several ways.
38 First, researchers noted an issue with medical ethics. It pertains to excessive service by
39 prescription of unnecessary medical treatments and procedures (Connell, 2013). Second,
40 there is growing skepticism in academia towards the holistic, therapeutical approach
41 because several studies have reported their questionable outcomes (Turner, 2017; Pinilla
42 and Rodriguez-Caro, 2019). Third, several treatment solutions, including surrogacy, stem
43 cells, abortion, transplantation, and 'death tourism' (euthanasia), raise concern over patient
44 safety and human morality (Connell, 2013). Technologies avail the emergence of the new
45 medical approaches that are capable of addressing the ethical pitfalls of the wellness
46 medical niche. In this vein, precision medicine expansion driven by the advancements in
47 Data Science (Demiris et al., 2019) may become an appealing topic for academia.
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49

50 51 **Conclusions**

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53 Wellness tourism has been profuse and proliferating research theme in the recent 75
54 years. Its academic topicality is caused by the liaison with essential human properties, such
55 as health and wellbeing. Wellness tourism effects on social and economic wellbeing is
56 another reason for the increasing interest in this research area.
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59 In 2020, we are approaching a period of another 75 years of wellness tourism
60 research development. We presume that the above-reviewed future research trends will
receive a shift shortly. Given the current pace of wellness tourism evolution (Nefiodov,

2006), in our belief, there will be a myriad of the newly emerging and currently unknown research streams contributing to the scholarship of wellness tourism.

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Fig.1. Conceptual map of health and wellness tourism research

385x421mm (150 x 150 DPI)